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Improved Method for the Allelic Definition of C4A and C4B Polymorphism (HLA Class III)

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ABSTRACT

The polymorphism of the fourth component of human serum complement (C4) is well established at the proteinic level; at the DNA level in the analysis of C4A and C4B gene polymorphism, the PCR technique is not widely and routinely used because it is time consuming and still presents reproducibility problems. This is a serious problem because only PCR genotyping allows the establishment of Rodgers-Chido reverse antigenicity without the need for classical family segregation studies, whose samples are not always easy to obtain. The most

commonly used protocol requires an initial PCR followed by nested amplification of all the products supposed positive or negative. The two reactions are set up using differing cycling conditions, primers, and magnesium chloride concentrations. We developed a simplified procedure to easily obtain reproducible results and used a single protocol for all reactions. Nested PCR is made using only the positive samples, so we decrease the number of samples to handle, the time spent for the work, and the reagents used for the reactions. Moreover, we increased the reproducibility of the experiments.

INTRODUCTION

The fourth component of human serum complement (C4) is coded for by two tandemly arranged genes expressing the two isotypes, C4A and C4B, respectively. These genes are located in the class III region of the major histo-

compatibility complex between HLA-B and HLA-DR loci. C4 is the most polymorphic of the human complement components with more than 35 alleles, including null alleles (C4*QO) at both genes (8). The proteinic polymorphism is usually analyzed employing high-voltage agarose gel electrophoresis (HVAGE) of neuraminidase-treated plasma samples (1), and the allotypes are defined by their relative positions after electrophoresis [i.e., the differences in net charge of the functionally active proteins (4,5)]. C4 polymorphism can be further described by the Rodgers (Rg) and Chido (Ch) antigens (the C4 proteins on red blood cells), which can be distinguished in serology with human alloantisera usually obtained from blood-transfused patients deficient for one of the C4 isotypes. These antigenic determinants are located in the C4d fragment of the α -chain (7). Rg is associated with C4A and Ch

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with C4B, but reverse antigenicity has been observed (3). The molecular basis for this antigenic polymorphism has been revealed by C4 cDNA sequencing and genomic sequences (9). The relevant sequence differences are located at four polymorphic sites within exons 25–28 of the C4 gene, as shown in the work by Barba et al. (2). In the present work, we follow the same nomenclature for the antigens and primers denominations. The fourth conformational epitope, WH, depends on the presence of Rg1 and Ch6 in the same C4 molecule. At the 7th Complement Genetics Workshop (Mainz, Germany; 1998) (5), it was agreed that the C4 isotype definition should be based on the absence or presence of Ch4: Ch⁻⁴ defines C4A and Ch⁺⁴ defines C4B isotype. Recently, a PCR-based method allowing the direct typing of Rg/Ch determinants was described (2). This method combines isotype and allele-specific amplification using sequence specific primers (SSP-PCR) and greatly facilitates the detection of recessive determinants not defined by specific antisera (e.g., the absence of Ch5, or Ch-5), which could otherwise only be detected in homozygotes or by carrying out extensive family studies using rare human alloantisera. The aim of this work is to simplify the method proposed by Barba et al. (2) for C4 typing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DNA Samples

Ten DNA samples from healthy donors during the 7th Complement Genetics (5) were received from various European laboratories. The DNA was extracted from EDTA blood, aliquoted, and stored at -70°C until shipment in dry ice to our laboratory.

PCR Protocol

The reaction was set up in a 10- μ L volume containing 50 mM KCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl, 0.1% Triton[®] X-100, 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 200 μ M each dNTP, 200 ng each primer, 50 ng genomic DNA, 0.5 U *Taq* DNA polymerase (Promega, Madison, WI, USA).

The primer combinations used for

the first reaction are A-down/Rg1, A-down/Ch1, B-down/Ch1, and B-down/Rg1. The expected size of the amplification products is 480 bp. As internal control, we used DRB 5' primer in combination with DRB 3' primer. The expected size of the amplification product is 187 bp.

To obtain complete genotype information we have used Ch5/-5 together with B-up/A-up primers for the Ch5/-5 determinants.

We used a Hybaid[®] model TR1 thermal cycler (Hybaid, Teddington, UK) and the following cycling protocol: a first denaturation step of 94°C for 1 min was followed by 35 cycles at 94°C for 30 s, 70°C for 45 s, and 72°C for 1 min.

Each amplification product (5 μ L) was loaded onto a 2% (w/v) Seakem[®] agarose gel (BMA, Rockland, ME, USA) with TAE buffer containing 0.5 mg/mL (w/v) of ethidium bromide and electrophoresed at 5 V/cm for 2 h.

Nested PCR

Amplification products for which we observed the presence of the expected band were diluted 1:1000. One microliter of this dilution was then subjected to a nested amplification using the following primer sets: Rg3/Rg1, Rg3/Ch1, Ch6/Ch1, and Ch6/Rg1. The expected size of the amplification products was 120 bp.

The PCR protocol is the same described for the first amplification. As internal control, we used DRB 5' primer in combination with DRB 3' primer. The expected size of the amplification product is 229 bp. Amplification products were visualized as already described. Primer sets used in the two reactions are summarized in Table 1.

RESULTS

A set of four isotype-specific primers has been designed (2) to amplify separately the C4d region of the two isotypes (A and B) of the C4 genes. Since the Ch4 sequence is always present in C4B and absent in C4A (10), two sets of primers, containing the Ch+4- or Ch-4-specific sequence, respectively, are normally chosen for typing. Each isotype-

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Table 1. Sequences of Primers Used in DNA Typing of C4 Samples

Primer	
Name	Sequence
A-down	aggaccctctccagtgtagac
B-down	aggacctctccagtgatacat
Rg1	agggtgtgtgggcaacaccga
Ch1	agggtgtgtgggcaacaccccg
Rg3	agcctccatctcaaaggcaaa
Ch6	agcctccatctcaaaggcaag
DRB 5'	caatgggacggagcgggtg
DRB 3'	gtctgcagtaggtgccca
DRB E	gccgctgcactgtgaagct

specific set is constituted by two primers, one directed upstream and the other downstream. Following this method, it is possible to determine the isotype and moreover subtyping the serologically defined C4 alleles (6).

Analysis of C4 Genes

A-up and B-up primers (see Materials and Methods) have been employed together with Rg1 and Ch1 primers, respectively, to amplify nearly all the C4d region (480 bp) in C4A and C4B genes. Rg3 and Ch6 primers have been employed for nested PCR using the 480-bp template. The product is about 120 bp in length. We typed Rg3 and Ch6 by nested PCR. Figure 1 shows the results of the two PCR assays on samples AR15 and NBW. The upper (A) panel shows the products of the first reactions, which have the expected size; the lower (B) panel shows the products of the nested amplifications, which also have the correct size. Table 2 compares the results obtained using our method and the one recommended by the 7th Complement Genetics Workshop (5). The two methods obtained the same results.

DISCUSSION

To perform the Rg/Ch typing, Barba et al. (2) have proposed a method with a first step constituted by four reactions for Rg1/Ch1 typing with differing primer combinations and differing magne-

Table 2. C4 Typing Results of the 7th Complement Genetics Workshop (5)

Summary of the Rg/Ch Genotyping Results									
		A				B			
Name	Primers	Ch1	Ch6	Rg1	Rg3	Ch1	Ch6	Rg1	Rg3
XR	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
XR	B-Down	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
DG25	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
DG25	B-Down	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
TS	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
TS	B-Down	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
GR	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
GR	B-Down	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
AR15	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
AR15	B-Down	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
JC	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
JC	B-Down	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
JDR	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
JDR	B-Down	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-
KH	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
KH	B-Down	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NBW	A-Down	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
NBW	B-Down	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+
BS	A-Down	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
BS	B-Down	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Comparison between our results (A) and those obtained by Barba et al. (2) (B).

sium concentrations. The second step is constituted by two nested amplifications (with differing primers combinations and magnesium concentrations), using as templates the amplification products of the first reactions, without analyzing them by gel electrophoresis. This means that both positive and negative samples are nested-amplified. This method implies great expenses in reagents and a very large number of tubes to handle, even double or triple compared with our method. In particular, many nested reactions without starting template (the 480-bp band) are performed. This effort may be avoided if the result of the first amplification with A/B-down and Rg1/Ch1 primers is checked before the planning of our last and unique nested PCR.

We developed a simplified typing procedure with two different steps. First, the A/B-down and Rg1/Ch1 de-

terminants are characterized and the products visualized by gel-electrophoresis; second, only the appropriate amplification products of the first PCR round are further characterized through the nested reaction.

Moreover, we changed the PCR conditions used by Barba et al. and developed a unique PCR protocol for both reactions (see Materials and Methods). Our protocol also employed a smaller reaction volume: in fact, our reactions are performed in a volume of 10 μ L, while the previous ones were performed in a volume of 50 μ L.

These modifications allowed us to reduce the number of tubes to handle and to simplify the whole procedure. Using this modified technique, we obtained reliable results. See Table 2 for a comparison of the data obtained using our simplified method and the typing results obtained at the 7th Complement

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Figure 1. C4 PCR amplification products. The upper side of the figure (A) shows electrophoretic pattern of the PCR products using samples AR15 with the following primers: A-down/Ch1 (lane 2), A-down/Rg1 (lane 3), B-down/Rg1 (lane 4), and B-down/Ch1 (lane 5). The positive internal control is obtained by using DRB 5' and DRB 3' primers (187 bp). The negative control is shown in lane 6. The marker (lane 1) used is a 100-bp ladder (MBI Fermentas). The lower side of the figure (B) shows the nested PCR of lane 3 with Rg1/Ch6 (lane 8) and Rg1/Rg3 (lane 9) and the nested PCR of lane 5 with Rg3/Ch1 (lane 10) and with Ch1/Ch6 (lane 11). The positive control is obtained by using DRB 5' and DRB E primers. The negative control is shown in lane 12. The marker (lane 7) used is a 100-bp ladder (MBI Fermentas, Vilnius, Lithuania).

the Rodgers and Chido antigenic determinants and their correlation with the human complement component C4A/C4B isotypes. *Immunogenetics* 27:399-405.

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Genetics Workshop published by Mauff et al. (5). It should be noted that the typing results we obtained using the simplified technique match perfectly those obtained using the original method. Therefore, we propose the use of the simplified technique, which is reliable, fast, and cheap for the genomic typing of human complement component C4.

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